

A Counting Problem of Perspective Simplexes In $PG(n, q)$

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Abstract

We start with a tetrahedron $(A) = A_1A_2A_3A_4$ in $PG(3, q)$, q is not a power of 2, and a point P not on the faces of (A) and found that the number of non-degenerate tetrahedrons that are perspective with (A) from the centre P and exclusive of the points P and A_i s is equal to $(q-1)^4 - 5$. If these tetrahedrons can have one of their vertices as P then the number of such non-degenerate tetrahedrons that are perspective with (A) from the centre P is equal to $4(q-1)^3$. These propositions are proved analytically using the homogeneous coordinates of the vertices of the tetrahedrons and other counting results in finite geometries. Further, the propositions are generalised to $PG(n, q)$ with cases $n \leq q$ and $n > q$.

Key Words: Finite Projective Geometry, Perspective Tetrahedrons, Perspective Simplexes, Homogeneous Coordinates.

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1. Introduction

Projective space

Let V be a $(n+1)$ -dimensional vector space over the field F . Let $PG(n, F)$ be the set of all 1-dimensional subspaces of V . A subset C of $PG(n, F)$ is said to be a subspace of $PG(n, F)$ if there is a subspace H of V such that C coincides with the set of all 1-dimensional subspaces of H . In this case dimension of C is d if the subspace H has dimension $d+1$. The set $PG(n, F)$ on which the concept of subspace is so defined is called an n -dimensional projective space on V or a projective space defined over F . [1]

A set of $n+1$ points in $PG(n, F)$ where no n of them are on the same $(n-1)$ -dimensional subspace is called a simplex. For $n=2$, the simplex is a triangle and for $n=3$, it is a

tetrahedron. Let $(A) = A_1A_2 \dots A_{n+1}$ be the simplex of reference and $U = \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} A_i$ be the unit

point of a frame of a $PG(n, F)$. Any point in $PG(n, F)$ can be expressed by a set of $n+1$ homogeneous coordinates with respect to this reference frame. As per the properties of homogeneous coordinates, an ordered $(n+1)$ -tuple $X = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n+1})$ as well as $\lambda X = (\lambda x_1, \lambda x_2, \dots, \lambda x_{n+1})$, $\lambda \neq 0$, represent the same point; [2]. Let $(B) = B_1B_2 \dots B_{n+1}$ be another simplex. With respect to the given frame the homogeneous coordinates of vertices of (B) can be expressed as follows

$$B_i = (b_{i1}, b_{i2}, \dots, b_{i(n+1)}), i = 1, 2, \dots, n+1$$

A square matrix M of order $n + 1$ with respect to the specified frame represents the simplex (B) if the coordinates of B_i are regarded as the elements of the i th row of a square matrix M of order $n + 1$; [3]. Now, the representation of the matrix (B) concerning the simplex (A) is denoted as $(B)_A = ((b_{ij}))$, $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n + 1$.

Perspective Simplexes

Two simplexes (A) and (B) in $PG(n, F)$ are said to be perspective or homological [4] if the lines joining their corresponding vertices are concurrent at a point P . In this case, the intersections of their corresponding prime faces lie on a prime p . P and p are called the centre of perspectivity and prime of perspectivity respectively. [5]

Let $P = (p_1, p_2, \dots, p_{n+1})$ and $B_i = \lambda_i A_i + P$, $\lambda_i \in F$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n + 1$. Taking $\lambda_i + p_i = a_i$ the coordinates of B_i becomes $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n+1})$ where

$$x_j = \begin{cases} a_j & j = i \\ p_j & j \neq i \end{cases}$$

Therefore

$$(B)_A = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 & p_2 & p_3 & \dots & p_{n+1} \\ p_1 & a_2 & p_3 & \dots & p_{n+1} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ p_1 & p_2 & p_3 & \dots & a_{n+1} \end{bmatrix}$$

or in symbol

$$(B)_A = \frac{(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{n+1})}{(p_1, p_2, \dots, p_{n+1})}. [3]$$

Finite Geometry

If the field F is finite with q elements, where q is the power of a prime, then the Projective Space is denoted by $PG(n, q)$. In $PG(n, q)$, the number of subspaces of dimension r is given by the expression:

$$\prod_{k=0}^r \frac{(q^{n+1} - q^k)}{(q^{r+1} - q^k)}. [6]$$

In particular, when $n = 3$, a $PG(3, q)$ contains $q^3 + q^2 + q + 1$ points and the same number of planes [7]. The number of lines in a $PG(3, q)$ is $(q^3 + q^2 + q + 1) \frac{(q^n - 1)}{(q^2 - 1)}$. In $PG(3, q)$, every

line will have $q + 1$ points on it, and every plane will have $q^2 + q + 1$ points on it. Also, every plane will have $q^2 + q + 1$ lines on it. [2]

In $PG(3, q)$, the 4×4 matrix given as $\begin{bmatrix} a_1 & p_2 & p_3 & p_4 \\ p_1 & a_2 & p_3 & p_4 \\ p_1 & p_2 & a_3 & p_4 \\ p_1 & p_2 & p_3 & a_4 \end{bmatrix}$ represents a tetrahedron (B) which is

perspective with the reference tetrahedron (A) from the centre $P(p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4)$.

2. Perspective Tetrahedrons in PG(3, q)

Let $(A) = A_1A_2A_3A_4$ be a non-degenerate tetrahedron in PG(3, q), where q is a prime power other than a power of 2. For the present study, it is required that the characteristic of the field is not equal to 2; hence, the assumption that q is not a power of 2 is required. Let $P(p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4)$ be a point not on any face of (A) . So, we have $p_i \neq 0, i = 1, 2, 3, 4$. To construct a tetrahedron $(B) = B_1B_2B_3B_4$ which will be perspective with (A) from the centre P we have to pick up four points, one each, from the four lines $A_iP, i = 1, 2, 3, 4$. In the first case, we take these points to be different from A_i s and P .

As each line A_iP has $q + 1$ points, so there are $q - 1$ points on this line other than A_i and P . So, when we chose one point each from each of these four lines, other than A_i and P then there will be $(q - 1)^4$ tetrahedrons which are perspective with (A) from the centre P . However, some of them will degenerate into coplanar points, not creating any non-degenerate tetrahedrons. To identify those, let us consider the expression of such a tetrahedron (B) considering (A) as the tetrahedron of reference. We have

$$(B)_A = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 & p_2 & p_3 & p_4 \\ p_1 & a_2 & p_3 & p_4 \\ p_1 & p_2 & a_3 & p_4 \\ p_1 & p_2 & p_3 & a_4 \end{bmatrix}$$

The tetrahedron (B) will be a degenerate tetrahedron if the above matrix exhibits the following:

- i) Sum of all rows is zero, i.e. $3p_i + a_i = 0, \forall i = 1, 2, 3, 4$. We have exactly one tetrahedron of this form.
- ii) Sum of any three rows is equal to the other row, i.e. $3p_i = a_i$ for one i and $2p_j + a_j = p_j \Rightarrow p_j + a_j = 0, \text{ for } j \neq i$. Under this case, there are 4 tetrahedrons, one for each i .
- iii) Sum of any three rows is equal to zero, which is not possible as it will make $3p_i = 0$ for some i , implying that q must be a power of 3, along with $2p_j + a_j = 0, j \neq i$. In that case, it forces that $a_j = p_j, j \neq i$ resulting three of the points same, hence a degenerate tetrahedron.
- iv) Sum of any two rows is equal to one of the other two, i.e., $2p_i = p_i \forall i$, which is not possible as $p_i \neq 0$.

So, we have proved the following Theorem.

Theorem 1: Let $(A) = A_1A_2A_3A_4$ be a non-degenerate tetrahedron in PG(3, q), where q is a prime power other than a power of 2. Let $P(p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4)$ be a point not any face of (A) . Then there are $(q - 1)^4 - 5$ number of tetrahedrons, with vertices exclusive of P and A_i s, which are perspective with (A) from the centre P .

Now, let us consider the case where one of the vertices of a tetrahedron so generated can be P . In that case, out of the four vertices, one vertex is P and the other three vertices are chosen from any three lines out of the four lines A_iP . As we have only $q - 1$ number of points to

choose from, there will be $\binom{4}{3}(q - 1)^3 = 4(q - 1)^3$ tetrahedrons which are perspective with (A)

from the centre P . Let us further investigate to find out the number of degenerate tetrahedrons among these to get the number of non-degenerate tetrahedrons. For this, let us consider the matrix representation of (B) as given above, with a change that exactly one of the a_i will be equal to p_i , i.e. one of the columns will have all elements equal to p_i for some i . The tetrahedron (B) will be a degenerate tetrahedron if the above matrix exhibits the following

- i) Sum of all rows is zero, i.e. $4p_i = 0$, for one i . Which is not possible as $p_i \neq 0$ and q is not a power of 2.
- ii) Sum of any three rows is equal to the other row, i.e. $3p_i = p_i$ for one or $2p_i = 0$, which is not possible because of the same reason as in (i).
- iii) Sum of any three rows is equal to zero, which is not possible, as it will make $3p_i = 0$ for some i , implying that q must be a power of 3 along with $2p_j + a_j = 0, j \neq i$. In that case, it forces that $a_j = p_j, j \neq i$ resulting three of the points same, hence a degenerate tetrahedron.
- iv) Sum of any two rows is equal to zero or equal to a third row. In this case $p_i = 0$ or $2p_i = 0$, which is not possible for similar reasons as in (i) & (ii).

Hence, we have proved the following Theorem.

Theorem 2: Let $(A) = A_1A_2A_3A_4$ be a non-degenerate tetrahedron in $PG(3, q)$, where q is prime power other than a power of 2. Let $P(p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4)$ be a point not on any face of (A) . Then there are $4(q-1)^3$ tetrahedrons, with one of the vertices equal to P , which are perspective with (A) from the centre P .

3. Perspective Simplexes in $PG(n, q)$

Now, we attempt to carry Theorem 1 into $PG(n, q)$. With the same assumptions, we now state the following theorem for simplexes in $PG(n, q)$, q is not a power of 2.

Theorem 3: Let $(A) = A_1A_2...A_nA_{n+1}$ be a non-degenerate simplex in $PG(n, q)$, where q is prime power other than a power of 2. Let $P(p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n, p_{n+1})$ be a point not on any face of (A) . Then there are 't' simplexes, which are perspective with (A) from the centre P , where

a) $t = (q-1)^{n+1} - n - 2$, if $n \leq q$

b) $t = (q-1)^{n+1} - n - 2 - \sum_{k=mq+1}^{n+1} \binom{n+1}{k} (n-k+1)$, where $m = 1, 2, \dots, \left\lfloor \frac{n}{q} \right\rfloor - 1$, if $n > q$

Proof: We have

$$(B)_A = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 & p_2 & p_3 & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & p_n & p_{n+1} \\ p_1 & a_2 & p_3 & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & p_n & p_{n+1} \\ p_1 & p_2 & a_3 & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & p_n & p_{n+1} \\ \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot \\ p_1 & p_2 & p_3 & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & a_n & p_{n+1} \\ p_1 & p_2 & p_3 & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & p_n & a_{n+1} \end{bmatrix}$$

Case-I: For $n = q$

- i) Sum of all rows is zero i.e. $np_i + a_i = 0, \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, n+1$. We have exactly one simplex of this form.
- ii) Sum of any n rows is equal to the other row i.e. $np_i = a_i$ for one i and $(n-1)p_j + a_j = p_j \Rightarrow (n-2)p_j + a_j = 0, \text{ for } j \neq i$. Under this case, there are $n + 1$ simplexes, one for each i .
- iii) Sum of any n rows equal to zero, which is not possible as it will make $np_i = 0$ for some i implying that q must be a power of n along with $(n-1)p_j + a_j = 0, j \neq i$. In that case, it forces that $a_j = p_j, j \neq i$ resulting n of the points same, hence a degenerate simplex.
- iv) Sum of any $(n-1)$ rows is equal to any one of the other two, i.e., $(n-1)p_i = p_i \Rightarrow (n-2)p_i = 0, \forall i$, which is not possible as $p_i \neq 0$.

Case-II: For $n < q$

- i) Sum of all rows is zero i.e. $np_i + a_i = 0, \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, n+1$. We have exactly one simplex of this form.
- ii) Sum of any n rows is equal to the other row i.e. $np_i = a_i$ for one i and $(n-1)p_j + a_j = p_j \Rightarrow (n-2)p_j + a_j = 0, \text{ for } j \neq i$. Under this case there are $n + 1$ simplexes, one for each i .
- iii) Sum of any k rows equal to zero, i.e. $kp_i = 0$, which is not possible as $k < q$.
- iv) Sum of any k rows is equal to any one of the other rows, i.e., $kp_i = p_i \Rightarrow (k-1)p_i = 0, \forall i \text{ where } k < n$, which is not possible as $p_i \neq 0$.

Case-III: For $n > q$

- i) Sum of all rows is zero, i.e. $np_i + a_i = 0, \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, n+1$. We have exactly one simplex of this form.
- ii) Sum of any k rows is equal to one of the other $(n + 1 - k)$ rows, where $q < k \leq n$. If the other row is the j^{th} row, then $kp_j = a_j$.

Let these k numbers be r_1, r_2, \dots, r_k , then for $i = r_1, r_2, \dots, r_k$, $(k-1)p_i + a_i = p_i \Rightarrow (k-2)p_i + a_i = 0$

For $i \neq r_1, r_2, \dots, r_k, j$, we have $kp_i = p_i \Rightarrow (k-1)p_i = 0 \Rightarrow (k-1)$ is a multiple of q .

$$\text{Hence } k = mq + 1, m = 1, 2, 3, \dots, \left\lfloor \frac{n}{q} \right\rfloor.$$

Conclusion

Counting different geometrical entities and structures in $PG(n, q)$ is always fascinating. As a part of our planned study, we have started counting multi-perspective simplexes in $PG(2, q)$ and $PG(3, q)$ and some interesting outcomes are there to share.

Declarations

Conflict of interest/Competing interests: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Hirschfeld, J. W. P., Projective Geometry Over Finite Fields, Charendon Press, Oxford, 1979.
- [2] Payne, S. E., Topics in Finite Geometry: Ovals, Ovoids and Generalized Quadrangles, University of Colorado Denver, 2007.
- [3] Sanyal, A. And Misra, S. K., Veronesian Pair and Associated Desmic System, Journal of Mathematical & Physical Sciences, 23, 1989, 161-169.
- [4] Court, N. A., Desargues And His Strange Theorem, Scripts. Maths., 20(1954), 1-20.
- [5] Gerber, L., Associated and Perspective Simplexes, Transactions of American Mathematical Society, 201, 1975, 43-55.
- [6] Carmichael, R. D., Introduction to The Theory of Finite Order, Dover, New-York, pp-108, 1956.
- [7] Coxeter, H.S.M., Introduction to Geometry, John Wiley, New York, 1961.